

DRIVING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH EXTERNAL CAPITAL: A CROSS-COUNTRY ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This study explored the various sources of foreign capital as they affect the economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana for the period 1990 to 2020. The various sources of foreign capital considered were foreign direct investment, external debt, official development assistance/aid, and remittances. In executing the study, we utilized the Fisher Cointegration test, panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach, fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) approach, and the Pairwise Dumitrescu Hurlin Panel Causality Test as techniques of analysis. Findings of the study revealed that there exists a long-run relationship and causal relationship between all the external capital sources and economic growth. Further, the result of the ARDL model indicated that all the external capital sources exerted a positive and significant long-run effect on economic growth. It follows from the findings of this study that external capital sources could be a veritable source of capital in stimulating the long-run economic growth of the two countries, as it will help in bridging the saving-investment gap which is sacrosanct for investment and growth.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment, Official Development Assistance, Remittances, External Debt, Economic Growth.

JEL Classification: C23; E22; F24; F35; F43; H63; O47.

1. Introduction

One key question is: Can external capital help in promoting economic growth of a nation? External capital is viewed as the set of real or financial resources that empower a nation to overcome its capital deficit [1]. Put differently, it is those set of finances that aid in bridging the savings-investment gap that is noticeable in most developing economies. The International Monetary Fund (IMF), have categorized external capital into two broad perspectives. These are: financial capital (foreign debt, official development assistance, concessional or non-concessional financial flows, portfolio investment, etc.) and foreign direct investment [2].

Two streams of arguments are prevalent on the effect of external capital on economic growth. The first streams of studies associated with [3] centres on the positive effect of external capital on the domestic economy; while the second streams associated with [4] is on the negative effect of external capital on the domestic economy. The positive effect of external capital on the domestic economy centres on the idea that capital mobility permits countries with inadequate savings resources to receive financing for their domestic investment projects [1], and it allows investors to diversify their portfolios, spread risk and trade inter-temporally [5]. As noted by [6], the inflow of external capital engenders diversification and improved risk management since economic agents have access to both external and internal sources of financing their investment ideas.

With respect to the second line of argument which sees external capital as being detrimental to economic growth, two perspectives associated with capital inflows are recognized globally. These are: crowding out effect, and financial instability [1]. External capital inflow is believed to stir a decline in domestic investment (i.e., crowding out effect) as such will replace domestic

investment, especially when it is geared towards a sector with concentration of a large chunk of domestic firms. However, [7] has noted that such multinational firms' entry could engender an upsurge in domestic investments in order to cope with competition from the foreign firms.

A key explanation is that foreign firms override domestic firms due to their advanced technology. In that regard, foreign investment will "crowd out" the investment of domestic firms and even instigate bankruptcy rather than a surge in their investment [1]. Another pertinent argument which was put forward by [8] and [9] against the entry of foreign firms into a domestic market, is that such have the capacity to disrupt financial market stability which will in turn affects economic growth negatively.

While some studies have been conducted to ascertain the effect of foreign direct investment on economic growth [10; 11; 12;13; 14; 15; and 16], effect of external debt on economic growth [17; 18; 19; 20; 21; 22; 23; 24; 25; and 26], effect of remittances on economic growth [see 13; 14; 15; 27; 28; 29; 30; 31; 32; 33; 34; 35; 36; 37; 38; 39; 40; 41; 42; 43; 44; 45; 46; and 47], and effect of foreign aid on economic growth [48; 49; 50; 51; 52; 53; and 54]; there have been variants in their findings as concerning the nature of the effect. This raises the concern for further studies that will bridge this gap. Also, the study is derived from the need to bridge the savings-investment gap experienced by developing economies as enshrined in the Harrod-Domar growth model.

Consequently, this study seeks to answer a key question that can drive policy formulations within the economy of Nigeria and Ghana. Should we depend on external debt, official development assistance/aid, remittances or foreign direct investment as a source of

external capital for growth? It is in this regard that this study seeks to examine the effect of foreign capital on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana. In specific terms, the study seeks to: (i) ascertain the effect of external debt on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana; (ii) evaluate the influence of foreign direct investment on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana; (iii) investigate the influence of remittances on the economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana; and (iv) examine the effect of official development assistance/aid on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana. This paper is presented in five sections: the first section handles the introductory issues and arguments in the literature and earlier findings; the stylized facts on external capital and

growth are captured in the second section; the third section discusses the methodology of the research; section four reports the empirical findings; and section five deals on the conclusion of the study.

2. Stylized Facts

The stylized facts capture the values of different external capital sources and the value of GDP in the two countries for selected years. These sources include external debt, foreign direct investment, remittances, and official development assistance.

2.1. External Debt Stock

The value of external debt stock for the case of Nigeria and Ghana is reflected in Table 1.

Table 1

External debt stocks, total (DOD, current US\$) for selected years.

Year	Nigeria	Ghana
1990	33,458,483,418.10	3,880,932,790.80
1995	34,094,439,060.40	5,935,777,124.30
2000	33,514,256,077.20	6,743,341,663.20
2005	29,099,132,314.50	7,334,787,205.40
2010	18,821,584,008.70	8,365,239,757.30
2015	32,413,453,871.70	20,073,270,363.80
2020	70,570,530,052.80	31,323,084,616.80

Source: World Development Indicators [55].

For Nigeria, external debt stock has been increasing though with periods of declining trend. For instance, it was valued at about US\$33.46 billion in 1990 and increased to US\$34.09 billion in 1995. This was

followed by a declining trend up to US\$18.82 billion in 2010 before a sharp increase to the tune of US\$70.57 billion was recorded in 2020. As a percentage of GDP, Figure 1 captures the trend over the study period.

Figure 1: Nigeria's external debt stock (% of GDP)

The total external debt stock (% of GDP) was volatile in the 1990s and early 2000s before a sharp decline was recorded in 10.76% in 2005 to 4.52% in 2006. Thereof, this ratio maintained an upward trend reaching 6.66% in 2015 and 14.29% in 2020. One notable feature is that this ratio is likely to maintain an upward trend given the continuous borrowing that is executed by the Nigerian government.

With respect to Ghana, the value of external debt stock was valued at US\$3.88 billion in 1990 and maintained a rising trend throughout the selected periods. It was valued at US\$7.33 billion in 2005, rose to US\$20.07 billion in 2015 with a further increase to US\$31.32 billion in 2020. As a percentage of GDP, Ghana exhibits a very high external debt as a ratio of GDP when compared to Nigeria. Figure 2 captures the trend of the external debt (% of GDP) during the study period.

Figure 2: Ghana's external debt stock (% of GDP)

The external debt (% of GDP) was somewhat stable in the 1990s and early 2000s as it was 29.47% in 1990 before rising slightly to 32.36% in 1995. The rising trend continued though with periods of slight decline up to 28.59% in 2005 before a sharp decline to 13.56% was recorded in 2006. After the recorded decline, the external debt stock (% of GDP) returned to an upward trend rising from 13.56% in 2006 to 23.79% in 2010 with a subsequent increase to 34.26% in 2013 and

41.23% in 2016. Between 2017 and 2020, the external debt stock (% of GDP) averaged 43.12% with the highest value of 49.94% being recorded in 2020.

2.2. Foreign Direct Investment

The volume of foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows in Nigeria and Ghana is reflected in Table 2 where the values are expressed based on the US\$ current balance of payments.

Table 2

Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$) for selected years

Year	Nigeria	Ghana
1990	587,882,970.63	14,800,000.00
1995	335,842,164.96	106,500,000.00
2000	1,140,167,556.02	165,900,000.00
2005	4,982,533,930.22	144,970,000.00
2010	6,026,253,091.35	2,527,350,000.00
2015	3,064,168,904.45	3,192,320,530.79
2020	2,385,277,665.92	1,875,782,953.47

Source: World Development Indicators [55].

At the current US\$, the value of FDI net inflows was US\$587.88 million in 1990 with a decline to US\$335.84 million in 1995. Subsequent years so captured reflect a rising trend given the increase to US\$1.14 billion, US\$4.98 billion, and US\$6.03 billion worth of FDI in 2000, 2005, and 2010 respectively. This rising trend ceased to continue for

2015 and 2020 as the value of net FDI inflows declined to US\$3.06 billion and US\$2.39 billion in the two periods respectively. A trend analysis of the movement of FDI (net inflows, % of GDP) has been following a downward trend in the recent years as could be seen from Figure 3.

Figure 3: Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)

In the 1990s, the ratio of the FDI net inflows to GDP was 1.09% but rose sharply to 5.79% in 1994 which was also followed by a sharp decline to 0.76% in 1995. Within 1995 and 2011, this ratio has been quite volatile before finally maintaining a downward trend up to 0.20% in 2018 before a mild increase to 0.55% was recorded in 2020.

The value of Ghana's FDI net inflow has been low compared to Nigeria, as the country recorded US\$14.80

million worth of FDI in 1990 and US\$165.90 million in 2000. This was followed by a decline to US\$144.97 million in 2005 before a sharp increase to US\$2.53 billion and US\$3.19 billion in 2010 and 2015 respectively. A substantial decline in the value of FDI net inflows of US\$1.88 billion was recorded in 2020. The FDI (net inflow, % of GDP) was quite low in the 1990s and early 2000s with high volatility as could be seen from Figure 4.

Figure 4: Ghana's foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)

After 2002, the FDI (net inflows, % of GDP) exhibited a sharp increase from 0.96% in 2002 to 9.47% in 2008 before a step-like decline began to set in thereafter. This step-like decline culminated to the ratio being 7.98% in 2012, 4.44% in 2018, and 2.74% in 2020.

2.3. Personal Remittances

The value of remittances received by individuals from Nigeria and Ghana is reflected in Table 3 where it is measured in current US dollar (US\$).

Table 3

Personal remittances, received (current US\$) for selected years

Year	Nigeria	Ghana
1990	10,008,540.02	6,000,000.00
1995	250,043,007.16	17,209,600.00
2000	1,391,826,072.14	32,396,800.00
2005	14,640,084,309.70	99,184,576.00
2010	19,744,755,062.59	135,852,160.00
2015	20,626,046,924.01	4,982,442,361.79
2020	17,207,547,306.00	4,291,956,800.56

Source: World Development Indicators [55].

It is glaring from Table 3 that the value of personal remittances received for the selected years has witnessed tremendous increase over the years. In Nigeria, it rose from US\$10.01 million in 1990 to US\$250.04 million in 1995 and then to US\$1.39 billion and US\$14.64 billion in 2000 and 2005 respectively. A further increase from US\$14.74 billion in 2005 to US\$19.74 billion and US\$20.63 billion in 2010 and 2015 were recorded respectively, before it plunged to US\$17.21 billion in 2020. Ghana also recorded a consistently rising value of remittances inflow into the

country as it increased from US\$6.00 million in 1990 to 17.21 million and 32.40 million in 1995 and 2000 respectively. This trend continued to US\$99.18 million and US\$135.85 million in 2005 and 2010 with a further rise to US\$4.98 billion in 2015 before it declined slightly to US\$4.29 billion in 2020.

A trend of personal remittances received (% of GDP) over the years is reflected in Figure 5 in which the ratio of remittances inflows to Ghana to GDP has been far below that of Nigeria over in the 1990s and in the early 2000s up to 2010.

Figure 5: Trend of personal remittances received (% of GDP)

The remittances received (% of GDP) averaged 1.00% and 0.26% for Nigeria and Ghana respectively between 1990 and 1999 but increased to 4.14% and 0.68% for the two countries respectively between 2000 and 2009. This ratio averaged 4.85% between 2010 and 2020 for Nigeria and 5.12% for Ghana between the same period. It can be observed from Figure 5 that the behaviour of this ratio has been less stable over the

years which indicates the volatility in the ratio for the two countries.

2.4 Official Development Assistance and Aid

Nigeria and Ghana have been receiving varying value worth of official development assistance (ODA) and foreign aid inflow into the country. Table 4 presents the value of such development assistance and aid for selected periods.

Table 4

Net official development assistance and official aid received (constant 2018 US\$)

Year	Nigeria	Ghana
1990	361,529,998.78	1,152,410,034.18
1995	250,380,004.88	691,000,000.00
2000	243,820,007.32	794,059,997.56
2005	6,792,169,921.88	1,577,410,034.18
2010	2,100,010,009.77	1,570,949,951.17
2015	2,520,199,951.17	1,061,260,009.77
2020	3,253,277,465.82	948,530,029.30

Source: World Development Indicators [55].

Consistent with Table 4, the ODA and foreign aid received in Nigeria was put at US\$361.53 million in 1990 against US\$250.38 million in 1995 which represents a 30.74% decline with a further decrease to US\$243.82 million in 2000. Though the ODA and aid received increased substantially to US\$6.79 billion in 2005, it was also followed by a sharp decline to US\$2.10 billion in 2010 before a slight increase to US\$2.52 billion and US\$3.25 billion was recorded in

2015 and 2020 respectively. For Ghana, ODA and aid received declined sharply from US\$1.15 billion in 1990 to US\$691.00 million in 1995 before a rising trend set in to US\$ 794.06 million and US\$1.58 billion in 2000 and 2005 respectively. This was followed by a continuous decline from US\$1.57 billion in 2010 to US\$1.06 billion and US\$948.53 million in 2015 and 2020 respectively. Figure 6 reflects on the trend of the value of ODA and aid received for the two countries.

Figure 6: Trend of net official development assistance and official aid received

It could be observed that for the two countries, the ODA and aid received has been very stable in the 1990s and early 2000s after which a divergence set in for Nigeria as it rose sharply and declined in the same manner in 2006. Subsequent years has been matched with a stable continuous rise for Nigeria while Ghana experiences steady decline recently.

2.5 Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

The performance of an economy is usually captured by the gross domestic product (GDP) of the nation. Table 5 reflects on the value of the GDP of Nigeria and Ghana for selected years.

Table 5

GDP (constant 2015 US\$) for selected years		
Year	Nigeria	Ghana
1990	151,245,202,579.56	13,167,489,322.53
1995	152,649,894,872.18	16,238,921,862.26
2000	177,407,437,761.56	20,062,228,699.60
2005	270,515,773,388.94	25,651,008,204.78
2010	380,985,472,030.91	35,165,253,297.98
2015	486,803,295,097.89	49,406,568,432.67
2020	493,917,966,761.43	62,724,594,622.78

Source: World Development Indicators [55].

Nigeria, being regarded as the giant of Africa, records an overwhelming high GDP value when compared with Ghana. In 1990, Nigeria recorded US\$151.25 billion GDP compared to Ghana with US\$13.17 billion; while in 1995, Nigeria recorded a GDP of US\$152.65 (0.93% growth) while Ghana recorded US\$16.24 billion (23.31% growth). The trend in the GDP of the two

countries has been on the rising pattern for the selected years up to 2020 where Nigeria recorded a GDP of US\$493.92 billion while Ghana recorded US\$62.72 billion in the same period.

As annual percentage growth, Figure 7 captures the trend of GDP growth of Nigeria and Ghana for the study period.

Figure 7: Trend of GDP growth rates (1990 – 2020)

It is clear from Figure 7 that there have been frequent changes in the growth rate of overall economic activities in the two countries. The data on 2020 indicates that the two countries experienced a declining trend in overall economic activities as can be observed from the downward trend in the figure. Given the instability in the trends of GDP growth so observed, it is pertinent to evaluate empirically the factors which could influence economic growth, with special emphasis on the role of external capital.

3. Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The two-gap model of Harrod and Domar forms the core justification most emerging nations struggle with either a lack of domestic saving to match investment possibilities or a lack of foreign currency to fund the purchase of capital and intermediate products [56]. A two-gap model suggests that external financing (that is, loans, grants, foreign direct investment, or remittances) can be critical in enhancing domestic resources and easing savings or foreign exchange constraints. This study utilizes the Harrod-Domar growth model's saving-investment theoretical gap paradigm, which was subsequently popularized by [57] and most recently used by [56]. According to the theory, developing nations may employ external inflows of capital, including remittances, to close the saving-investment gap [56].

Consistent with the two-gap model, saving equals investment at all time for equilibrium to be attained. Thus:

$$S_{i,t} = I_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

Where $S_{i,t}$ is the savings in country i at time t , and $I_{i,t}$ is the investment in country i at time t . However, actual saving is typically lower than investment in African nations (saving gap); as a result, external capital might be utilized to supplement the low saving level with investment as:

$$S_{i,t} + EXCP_{i,t} = I_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

Where $EXCP_{i,t}$ is the external capital in country i at time t . The capital stock equation that describes how saving affects capital stock is then given as:

$$K_{i,t} = S_{i,t} + EXCP_{i,t} + (1 - \gamma)K_{i,t-1} \quad (3)$$

In such situation, the following is how the Cobb-Douglas production function, which connects labour, technology, and capital stock to output, is expressed:

$$Y_{i,t} = AL_{i,t}^{1-\alpha} K_{i,t}^{\alpha} \quad (4)$$

Of which $Y_{i,t}$ is the gross domestic product (GDP) in country i at time t , $L_{i,t}$ is labour, and $K_{i,t}$ is the stock of capital.

By employing per capita terms, Equation (4) can be expressed as:

$$\frac{Y_{i,t}}{L_{i,t}} = \frac{AL_{i,t}^{1-\alpha} K_{i,t}^{\alpha}}{L_{i,t}} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{Y_{i,t}}{L_{i,t}} = A \left(\frac{K_{i,t}}{L_{i,t}} \right)^{\alpha} \quad (6)$$

Which can be written in a simplified form as:

$$y_{i,t} = Ak_{i,t}^{\alpha} \quad (7)$$

Of which $y_{i,t} = Y_{i,t}/L_{i,t}$ which is the output per labour, $k = K/L$ which is the capital per labour, and A is the exogenous technology which is fixed.

The above corresponds to the AK model ($Y = AK$) where long-run growth rate of an economy is correlated with its saving rate. For instance, if a given fraction 's' of output is saved and there is a set rate of depreciation γ , the rate of total net investment is:

$$\frac{dK}{dt} = sY - \gamma K \quad (8)$$

Consistent with the AK model and Equation (8), the growth rate will be given as:

$$g \equiv \frac{1}{Y} \frac{dY}{dt} = \frac{1}{K} \frac{dK}{dt} = As - \gamma \quad (9)$$

Consequently, an increase in the saving rate s will lead to a higher growth rate in the economy. It is the existence of the savings gap that the importance of external capital in spurring growth becomes valid as it is one of the sources of capital to bridge such gap.

3.2 The Model

The model for this study is specified based on the simple Cobb-Douglas production function with capital and labour input. The specific form of the model is specified as:

$$y_{i,t} = AK_{i,t}^{\alpha} L_{i,t}^{\beta} \quad (10)$$

Where y is the measure of aggregate output, K is capital, L is labour, A is efficiency parameter which captures technological progress, while α and β are the productivity coefficients which measures the returns to scale of capital and labour respectively. Equation (10) can be transformed into a linear function by introducing the logarithm as follows:

$$\ln y_{i,t} = \ln A + \alpha \ln K_{i,t} + \beta \ln L_{i,t} \quad (11)$$

By adapting the Cobb-Douglas production function to capture the objective of this study, the model is specified thus;

$$GDP_{i,t} = f(GFC_{i,t}, LBF_{i,t}, EXT_{i,t}, NRR_{i,t}, CPS_{i,t}, INF_{i,t}) \quad (12)$$

Where $EXT_{i,t}$ is a vector of external capital given as: $EXT_{i,t} = [EDS_{i,t}, FDI_{i,t}, REM_{i,t}, ODA_{i,t}]$.

The key definition of the variables in the model is given below:

GDP (constant 2015 US\$)	(GDP)
Labour force, total	LBF
Gross fixed capital formation (% of GDP)	GFC
External debt stocks, total (DOD, current US\$)	EDS
Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$)	FDI
Net official development assistance and official aid received (constant 2018 US\$)	ODA
Personal remittances, received (current US\$)	REM
Total natural resources rents (% of GDP)	NRR
Domestic credit to private sector (% of GDP)	CPS
Inflation, consumer prices (annual %)	INF

Equation (12) is transformed into a form amendable for estimation, and after introducing the natural long we have as follows:

$$\ln GDP_{i,t} = \delta_0 + \delta_1 GFC_{i,t} + \delta_2 \ln LBF_{i,t} + \delta_3 \ln EDS_{i,t} + \delta_4 \ln FDI_{i,t} + \delta_5 \ln REM_{i,t} + \delta_6 \ln ODA_{i,t} + \delta_7 NRR_{i,t} + \delta_8 CPS_{i,t} + \delta_9 INF_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{13}$$

Where *ln* is the natural log, *i* is the countries (*i* = 1, 2), *t* is time, δ'_s are the parameters to be estimated, and ε is the error term. It is worth noting that from Equation (13), we did not introduce the natural log to GFC, NRR, CPS, and INF. The reason for this is that these set of variables are already in rates and it is not necessary to log them again.

3.2 A Priori Expectation

It is expected that labour force, external capital sources, total natural resource rent, and domestic credit to the private sector should have a positive effect on growth ($\delta_2 > 0$; $\delta_3 > 0$; $\delta_4 > 0$; $\delta_5 > 0$; $\delta_6 > 0$; $\delta_7 > 0$; $\delta_8 > 0$); while capital-output ratio and inflation are expected to have a negative effect on economic growth ($\delta_1 < 0$ and $\delta_9 < 0$).

3.3 The Data

The data used for this study is a panel data with two cross sections (Nigeria and Ghana) and with thirty-one (31) observations cutting across 1990 to 2020, thus making a total of sixty-two (62) observations. The data is obtained strictly from the World Development Indicators which is a publication of the World Bank. The data is obtained on variables of interest which are GDP (constant 2015 US\$); Labour force, total; Gross fixed capital formation (% of GDP); External debt stocks, total (DOD, current US\$); Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$); Net official development assistance and official aid received (constant 2018 US\$); Personal remittances, received (current US\$);

Total natural resources rents (% of GDP); Domestic credit to private sector (% of GDP); and Inflation, consumer prices (annual %).

3.3 Technique of Analysis

Data for the study is analyzed firstly by using the panel data unit root test analysis to ascertain the order of integration of the variables. The panel unit root is conducted using two approaches – the individual unit root test approach developed by Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) [58], and the common unit root test approach developed by Levin, Lin and Chu (LLC) [59]. Further, the study utilizes the Johansen Fisher cointegration analysis and Kao cointegration analysis to ascertain the existence of long-run relationship in the model. Such therefore leads to the use of the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach to estimate the short-run dynamics and the long-run estimates of the model. For robustness check, the study also utilizes the cointegration regression under the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) to estimate the model. For the purpose of ascertaining the direction of causality among variables, the study utilizes the Dumitrescu-Hurlin Granger causality test with the null hypothesis that “Y does not homogeneously cause X”, where X and Y could be any variable of interest.

4. Empirical Results

4.1. Descriptive Analysis

The information contained in Table 6 reflects the descriptive properties of the variables employed in the study.

Table 6

Descriptive properties of the variables										
	lnGDP	GFC	lnLBF	lnEDS	lnFDI	lnREM	lnODA	NRR	CPS	INF
Mean	25.18	24.31	16.85	23.51	20.68	20.33	20.76	13.46	10.78	18.91
Maximum	26.94	53.12	17.95	24.98	22.90	23.91	23.20	31.77	19.63	72.84
Minimum	23.30	11.76	15.67	22.03	16.51	15.61	19.14	4.80	3.66	4.87
Std. Dev.	1.24	9.58	0.83	0.82	1.65	2.70	0.86	5.23	3.79	14.88
Skewness	-0.02	1.07	-0.02	-0.29	-0.76	-0.15	0.07	0.92	0.01	1.88
Kurtosis	1.50	3.58	1.25	1.78	2.62	1.69	3.01	4.14	2.19	5.90
Jarque-Bera	5.80	12.71	7.96	4.71	6.27	4.67	0.06	11.99	1.69	58.28
Probability	0.06	0.00*	0.02*	0.10	0.04*	0.10	0.97	0.00*	0.43	0.00*
Observations	62	62	62	62	62	62	62	62	62	62

Note: * denotes significance at the 5% level.

Source: Researchers’ computation (2023).

The log of GDP, measuring economic growth, maintained an average value of 25.18% with a standard deviation of 1.24% and having a minimum and maximum values of 23.30% and 26.94% respectively. The variable is negatively skewed given the skewness coefficient of -0.02 and is platykurtic. The variable is normally distributed given that the Jarque-Bera (JB) statistic is not significant at the 5% level. The gross fixed capital formation (GFC) being measured as a percentage of GDP maintained an average value of 24.31% and having a standard deviation of 9.58%. Its minimum value so reported is 11.76% while the maximum value is 53.12%; while the distribution is positively skewed

but leptokurtic, it is not normally distributed given that the JB statistic is significant at the 5% level. The log of labour force is seen to have a mean value of 16.85% and a standard deviation of 0.83%. Also, the numerical values of the variable ranges between 15.67% to 17.95% and its distribution is negatively skewed as well as being platykurtic. The distribution is not normally distributed as could be observed from the significance of the JB statistic at 5% level.

The log of external debt stock averaged 23.51% and having a standard deviation of 0.82%, with its values ranging between 22.03% to 24.98%. The distribution of the variable is negatively skewed given the -0.29

coefficient of skewness, and it is platykurtic in nature. However, the insignificance of the JB statistic at the 5% level portrays that the variable is normally distributed. For the log of foreign direct investment, its mean value is 20.68% and its standard deviation is 1.65%. The value of the variable ranges between 16.51% to 22.90%, while its distribution negatively skewed and platykurtic. Since the JB statistic is significant at the 5% level, the variable is not normally distributed.

The log of personal remittances received averaged 20.33% with a standard deviation of 2.70%, and its values ranges between 15.61% to 23.91%. The distribution is negatively skewed given that the skewness coefficient is -0.15, and it is platykurtic in nature as reported by the 1.69 coefficient of kurtosis. Meanwhile, the insignificance of the JB statistic at the 5% level renders the variable to be normally distributed. The log of official development assistance and aid received averaged 20.76% and having a standard deviation of 0.86%, while its value ranges between 19.14% to 23.20%. The variable exhibits a positively skewed distribution that is platykurtic in nature, and it is normally distributed as

could be noted from the insignificance of the JB statistic at the 5% level.

The value of the total natural resource rent (% of GDP) averaged 13.46% and has a standard deviation of 5.23, and its value ranges between 4.80% to 31.77%. The variable is positively skewed and leptokurtic, and it is not normally distributed. The credit to the private sector (% of GDP) representing the level of financial sector development has a mean value of 10.78% with a standard deviation of 3.79%, and its value ranges between 3.66% and 19.63%. The variable is positively skewed and is platykurtic, and it is normally distributed. Lastly, the rate of inflation averaged 18.91% with a standard deviation of 14.88%, and ranges between 4.87% to 72.84%. The values of the variable follow a positively skewed and leptokurtic distribution, and it is not normally distributed.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 7 captures the nature of correlation existing between variables in the model. The value of unity recorded in the Table indicates that a variable will always correlates perfectly with itself.

Table 7

Correlation matrix										
	lnGDP	GFC	lnLBF	lnEDS	lnFDI	lnREM	lnODA	NRR	CPS	INF
lnGDP	1									
GFC	0.173	1								
lnLBF	0.989	0.258	1							
lnEDS	0.855	0.395	0.841	1						
lnFDI	0.699	-0.113	0.623	0.574	1					
lnREM	0.820	-0.204	0.747	0.693	0.857	1				
lnODA	0.187	-0.645	0.089	-0.062	0.368	0.496	1			
NRR	0.258	0.592	0.320	0.302	0.154	0.036	-0.385	1		
CPS	0.121	-0.454	0.031	-0.010	0.550	0.479	0.463	-0.279	1	
INF	-0.140	0.266	-0.075	-0.050	-0.318	-0.351	-0.417	0.288	-0.522	1

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

Apart from the correlation between lnGDP and INF which is negative, the correlation between lnGDP and every other variable in the model is positive. This indicates that lnGDP correlates moves in an opposite direction with INF, but in the same direction with every other variable. In terms of the strength of the correlation, the correlation between lnGDP and lnLBF being +0.989, lnGDP and lnEDS being +0.855, lnGDP and lnFDI being +0.699, and lnGDP and lnREM being +0.820, are very strong, while that of lnGDP and GFC being +0.173, lnGDP and lnODA being +0.187, lnGDP and NRR being +0.258, lnGDP and CPS being +0.121, and lnGDP and INF are all exhibiting a very weak association. Since none of the explanatory variables exhibits a perfect linear correlation with each other, then the problem of multicollinearity in the model is likely

to be absent. Further, the existence of a strong or weak correlation does not in any way imply a cause-effect relationship. They only indicate the direction of movements of the variables involved. The regression analysis will aid in the determination of the cause-effect relationship that exists between the dependent variable and the explanatory variables in the model.

4.3 Unit Root Test Analysis

In order to ascertain the order of integration of the variables, the study employs both the individual unit root process developed by Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) [58], and the common unit root test approach developed by Levin, Lin and Chu (LLC) [59]. Table 8 reflects on the result, where I(0) implies that the variable is stationary at level and I(1) indicates that the variable is stationary at first difference.

Table 8

Variables	Unit root test result					
	Common Unit Root Test (LLC)		Order of Integration	Individual Unit Root Test (IPS)		Order of Integration
	Level	First Difference		Level	First Difference	
lnGDP	0.7961	-1.9839*	I(1)	0.3170	-2.6963*	I(1)
GFCF	1.6537	-4.9232*	I(1)	1.9419	-4.4111*	I(1)
lnLBF	3.1012	-2.0958*	I(1)	3.3597	-1.7202*	I(1)
lnEDS	1.6175	-4.9697*	I(1)	2.2704	-3.6762*	I(1)
lnFDI	1.0933	-2.4507*	I(1)	0.4242	-1.9750*	I(1)
lnREM	-1.4395	-6.4731*	I(1)	-1.0054	-6.8928*	I(1)
lnODA	-2.0569*	-----	I(0)	-2.0895*	-----	I(0)
CPS	-1.9181*	-----	I(0)	-0.4673	-7.0685*	I(1)
INF	-1.7473*	-----	I(0)	-2.0963*	-----	I(0)
NRR	-2.4990*	-----	I(0)	-2.9771*	-----	I(0)

Note: * denotes significance at 5% level; I(0) and I(1) denotes stationarity at levels and first difference respectively.

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

From the unit root test result presented in Table 8, it is indicated that the common unit root test result shows that lnGDP, GFCF, lnLBF, lnEDS, lnFDI, and lnREM became stationary after first difference hence, they are I(1) variables. However, lnODA, CPS, INF, and NRR were all stationary at level. Under the individual unit root test, the result indicates that lnGDP, GFCF, lnLBF, lnEDS, lnFDI, lnREM, and CPS were stationary at first difference while only lnODA, INF, and NRR were stationary at level. In both cases, it is clear that some variables are stationary at level while

others became stationary at first difference. This necessitates the need for a test for the existence of a long-run relationship among variables in the model.

4.4 Cointegration Analysis

The existence of a mixed order of integration at I(0) and I(1) among the variables necessitates the test for long-run relationship (cointegration) among the variables. Since our study is panel in nature, we deploy both the Johansen Fisher cointegration test and Kao residual cointegration analysis. Table 9A and 9B presents the result in both cases.

Table 9A

Johansen Fisher Panel Cointegration Test Result					
Hypothesized Number of Cointegrating Equations	Fisher Stat. (from Trace test)	Probability	Fisher Stat. (from Max-Eigen test)	Probability	
None	2.773	0.5966	2.773	0.5966	
At most 1	0.000	0.0000*	36.840	0.0000*	
At most 2	172.300	0.0000*	61.050	0.0000*	
At most 3	89.890	0.0000*	37.020	0.0000*	
At most 4	62.190	0.0000*	21.630	0.0002*	
At most 5	43.320	0.0000*	14.320	0.0063*	
At most 6	31.660	0.0000*	15.480	0.0038*	
At most 7	19.270	0.0007*	10.330	0.0352*	
At most 8	13.160	0.0105*	9.857	0.0429*	
At most 9	10.820	0.0286*	10.820	0.0286*	

Note: * denotes significance at 5%.

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

From the Johansen Fisher cointegration test result in Table 9A, both the Trace test and Max-Eigen statistic report the existence of nine cointegrating equations. Therefore, cointegration exists and there is a long-run relationship between economic growth and external

capital inflows in Nigeria and Ghana. To further prove the existence of cointegration, the Kao residual cointegration test is conducted and Table 9B captures the result.

Table 9B

Kao Residual Cointegration Result		
	t-Statistic	Probability
ADF	-3.2722	0.0005**
Residual variance	0.0011	
HAC variance	0.0009	

Note: ** denotes significance at 1%.

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

Since it could be observed from Table 9B that the ADF statistic is significant at the 1% level, the null hypothesis of “no levels relationship” is rejected and we conclude that there is a long-run relationship between economic growth and external capital inflows in Nigeria and Ghana. Consequently, our analysis proceeds to estimating both the short-run dynamic estimates and the long-run (levels) equation.

4.5 Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Estimation

Since the unit root test result indicate that some of our variables are stationary at level while others are stationary at first difference, and that there is a long-run

relationship among variables in the model, we proceed to estimate both the short-run dynamic estimates and the long-run estimates using the panel ARDL approach. This approach helps in the estimation of both the short-run and long-run estimates simultaneously.

4.5.1 Lag Order Selection

In order to determine the optimal lag length for our ARDL model, we deploy the lag selection approaches of Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), and Hannan-Quinn (HQ) criterion. The result is presented in Table 10 as follows.

Table 10

lag Order Selection Result Based on BIC and HQ					
Model	LogL	AIC	SIC	HQ	Specification
2	193.9525	-4.9984	-3.2576	-4.3203	ARDL(1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2)
1	172.7230	-4.8870	-3.7857	-4.4580	ARDL(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

It is clear from Table 10 that the Model with one lag, where the dependent variable has one lag and the explanatory variables also have one lag, is the best. This is because in the model with one lag, the SIC (-3.7857) is less than that of the model with two lags (-3.2576), and the HQ (-4.4580) is less than that of the model with two lags (-4.3203). Although the AIC in the model with two lags (-4.9984) is less than that of one

lag (-4.8870), the fact that the other two lag selection criterion has minimum values for a model with one lag renders Model 1 as the best.

4.5.2 Panel ARDL Estimation

The result of the panel ARDL model is presented in Table 11 as follows. The estimation is conducted based on ARDL(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1) as this lag order selection has the least BIC and HQ.

Table 11

Autoregressive distributed lag short-run and long-run result				
Selected Model: ARDL (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Probability
Long Run Equation				
GFC	-0.0055	0.0012	-4.7056	0.0000**
lnLBF	1.5113	0.0623	24.273	0.0000**
lnEDS	0.0894	0.0154	5.8165	0.0000**
lnFDI	0.0179	0.0053	3.3895	0.0019*
lnREM	0.0386	0.0077	4.9841	0.0000**
lnODA	0.1127	0.0194	5.7983	0.0000**
NRR	-0.0021	0.0019	-1.1187	0.2719
CPS	-0.0045	0.0023	-1.9810	0.0565
INF	-0.0005	0.0003	-1.4726	0.1510
Short Run Equation				
ECM_{t-1}	-0.3362	0.2231	-1.5068	0.1420
$\Delta(GFC)$	-0.0018	0.0034	-0.5253	0.6031
$\Delta(\ln LBF)$	0.4035	0.4626	0.8722	0.3898
$\Delta(\ln EDS)$	0.0075	0.0228	0.3302	0.7434
$\Delta(\ln FDI)$	-0.0044	0.0019	-2.2762	0.0299*
$\Delta(\ln REM)$	-0.0072	0.0070	-1.0218	0.3148
$\Delta(\ln ODA)$	-0.0158	0.0353	-0.4457	0.6589
$\Delta(NRR)$	-2.07E-05	0.0011	-0.0184	0.9854
$\Delta(CPS)$	0.0015	0.0017	0.9034	0.3733
$\Delta(INF)$	-0.0004	0.0006	-0.7393	0.4653
C	-1.8489	1.2218	-1.5133	0.1403

Note: ** and * denotes significance at 1% and 5% respectively.

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

The ARDL result presented in Table 11 has both the long-run and the short-run components. In the long-run, it is observed that capital-output ratio (measured as the ratio of gross fixed capital formation to GDP) exerts a negative and significant influence on economic

growth. This is inline with the prediction of the Harrod-Domar growth model where there is an inverse relationship between output growth and capital output ratio. Thus, a 1% increase in capital-output ratio will lead to 0.0055% decrease in economic growth. Also, labour

force exerts a positive and significant influence on economic growth and this meet the a priori expectation. Consequently, a 1% increase in labour input will lead to a 1.5113% increase in economic growth on the average. All the external capital inflows are observed to exert a positive and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. This finding is consistent with the works of [1] who observed a positive effect of external capital on the growth of countries within the Economic and Monetary Community of Central Africa (EMCCA). An increase in the inflows of these capital will lead to an increase in the overall economic growth. This positive effect is associated with the important role that these external capital inflows could play in bridging the savings-investment gap that is prevalent in these two economies. A 1% increase in external debt is associated with a 0.0894% increase in economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. Also, a 1% increase in foreign direct investment inflows will lead to a 0.0179% increase in economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. Further, a 1% increase in personal remittances received will lead to a 0.0386% increase in economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana in the long-run. Finally, a 1% increase in official development assistance and foreign aid received will lead to a 0.1127% increase in economic growth. Hence, Nigeria and Ghana and depend on these sources of external capital to drive their long-term economic growth agenda. The effect of total natural resource rent, credit to the private sector, and inflation rate are all negative and insignificant in influencing economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana in the long-run.

In the short-run, the capital-output ratio exerts a negative but insignificant influence on economic

growth while the effect of labour force is positive but insignificant. All the external capital sources, except external debt, are observed to exert a negative effect on growth in the short-run. Most importantly, changes in the foreign direct investment net inflows is observed to exert a negative and significant effect on the economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana in the short-run. This can be linked to the fact that multinationals could bring in their foreign technology that ensures minimum cost of production, which will also imply that they can sell their output at a lower price. In that case, local industries will not be able to compete favourable. This will lead to their sudden collapse which has a dampening effect on the domestic economic in the long-run. It follows that a 1% increase in foreign direct investment inflows will lead to a 0.0044% decrease in economic growth in the short-run. While the effect of total natural resource rent and inflation rate on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana is negative and insignificant in the short-run, the effect of credit to the private sector is positive but insignificant. The error correction term indicates that the model adjusts to achieve equilibrium in the long-run. Thus, 33.62% of the total short-run disequilibrium is corrected on an annual basis for the restoration of equilibrium in the long-run. It follows that it will take approximately three years for equilibrium in the model to be fully restored.

4.6 Robustness Estimation Using Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) Estimation

In order to ensure the robustness of our estimated model, we utilize the cointegration regression analysis under the FMOLS approach to estimate our model. Table 12 captures the result so obtained in the process.

Table 12

Robustness estimation result				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GFC	-0.0059	0.0026	-2.2697	0.0277*
LBF	1.3863	0.2878	4.8162	0.0000**
EDS	0.1729	0.0491	3.5224	0.0009**
FDI	0.0496	0.0176	2.8157	0.0070**
REM	-0.0096	0.0231	-0.4160	0.6792
ODA	0.0976	0.0255	3.8333	0.0004**
NRR	-0.0015	0.0036	-0.4065	0.6861
CPS	0.0013	0.0060	0.2127	0.8324
INF	-0.0006	0.0010	-0.5697	0.5715
R-squared	0.9965	Mean dependent var		25.2028
Adjusted R-squared	0.9958	S.D. dependent var		1.2384
S.E. of regression	0.0803	Sum squared resid		0.3158
Long-run variance	0.0071			

Note: ** and * denotes significance at 1% and 5% respectively.

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

From the result in Table 12, it is clear that the capital-output ratio still has a negative and significant effect on growth; while labour force has a positive and significant effect on growth. A 1% increase in the capital-output ratio will lead to a 0.0059% decline in economic growth; while a 1% increase in labour employment will lead to a 1.3863% increase in economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. Among the external capital sources, the result revealed that external debt, for-

ign direct investment, and official development assistance/aid exert positive and significant effect on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana while the effect of remittances is negative but insignificant. A 1% increase in external debt, foreign direct investment, and official development assistance/aid will respectively lead to a 0.1729%, 0.0496%, and 0.0976% increase in economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana. Meanwhile, the effect of total natural resource rent and inflation on economic

growth remain negative and insignificant, while the effect of credit to the private sector (% of GDP) remains positive but insignificant. The R-squared of 0.9965 indicates that the explanatory variables jointly explain 99.65% of the total variation in economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. This represents a good fit of the regression line.

4.7 Causality Test

In order to ascertain the direction of causality existing between economic growth and the external capital sources, the Dumitrescu-Hurlin Granger causality test is conducted and the result is presented in Table 13.

Table 13

Dumitrescu-Hurlin Granger causality test result			
Null Hypothesis:	W-Stat.	Zbar-Stat.	Probability
lnEDS does not homogeneously cause lnGDP	4.44669	2.93195	0.0034*
lnGDP does not homogeneously cause lnEDS	2.83248	1.52618	0.1270
lnREM does not homogeneously cause lnGDP	4.09579	2.62636	0.0086*
lnGDP does not homogeneously cause lnREM	8.25387	6.24751	0.0000**
lnFDI does not homogeneously cause lnGDP	3.84282	2.40606	0.0161*
lnGDP does not homogeneously cause lnFDI	0.76390	-0.2753	0.7831
lnODA does not homogeneously cause lnGDP	5.95975	4.24963	0.0000**
lnGDP does not homogeneously cause lnODA	3.79538	2.36474	0.0180*

Note: ** and * denotes significance at 1% and 5% respectively.

Source: Researchers' computation (2023).

From the result presented in Table 13, it can be observed that external debt stock causes economic growth but economic growth does not cause external debt stock. Thus, there is a unidirectional causality flowing from external debt to economic growth. It is also observed that personal remittances received causes economic growth, and economic growth also causes personal remittances received. Consequently, there is a bidirectional (two-way) causality between personal remittances received and economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. Also, foreign direct investment causes economic growth but economic growth does not cause foreign direct investment. Hence, a unidirectional causality (one-way) causality flows from foreign direct investment to economic growth. Lastly, official development assistance/aid is observed to cause economic growth but economic growth does not cause official development assistance/aid. Therefore, a unidirectional causality flows from official development assistance/aid to economic growth.

4.8 Policy Implication of Findings

The findings of this study have some implications for policy. The fact that external capital sources exert a positive and significant long-run effect on the economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana is an indication that these two West African countries can rely on external capital to push their growth agenda. One of the key things to note is that from the robust regression result, remittances have a negative but insignificant effect on economic growth. This can be a possibility since most often, remittances can be utilized for consumption instead of financing investment. Thus, this could not be a very reliable source of external capital for economic growth. Also, it is pertinent to note that external capital may not bring forth the immediate (short-term) impact on growth. This is because these capital flows need time to be fully deployed across critical sectors of the economy to be able to yield the desired result. It is also pertinent that the domestic economy must be ready to adapt appropriately to the short-term changes that may occur in the economy upon receiving this capital. This can be in the form of pressure on domestic production

as in the case of foreign direct investment, burden of debt servicing, and aligning policies with the requirement of the donor agencies. Consequently, external capital should be used in targeting long-term economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The Harrod-Domar growth model has stated that developing economies have a saving-investment gap. Thus, there is need to resort to external capital to bridge such gap. This external capital could be derived from external borrowing, foreign direct investment, remittances, and official development assistance/aid. This study is an attempt to explore how these sources of external financing could influence the economic growth of two critical West African economies which are Nigeria and Ghana. This study utilizes data from these two economies from 1990 to 2020 to empirically ascertain whether the aforementioned external capital sources could have an influence on the economic growth of the two countries.

The study utilizes the panel unit root test under the Im, Pesaran and Shin (for individual unit root process), and Levin, Lin and Chu (for common unit root test process) to explore the order of integration of the variables. Findings from the test indicates that some variables were stationary at level while others were stationary at first difference. The mixed order of integration gave the impetus to ascertain the existence of long-run relationship in the model. To do this, the study utilizes the Johansen Fisher panel cointegration test and the Kao residual cointegration test approaches. These two tests offered supporting evidence for the existence of long-run relationship in the model. We therefore explored the estimation of both the short-run and the long-run estimates of the model by using the panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model. The short-run result indicates that out of the four external capital sources so considered, only foreign direct investment had a significant effect on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana, though such effect is observed to be detrimental to growth. The short-run model is observed to adjust to

the tune of 33.62% on a yearly basis for equilibrium to be restored in the long-run.

The long-run result of the panel ARDL estimation indicates that all the external capital source (external borrowing, foreign direct investment, remittances, and official development assistance/aid) were drivers of economic growth as they all exerted a positive and significant influence on the economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana. This positive and significant influence so obtained passes through the bridging of the savings investment gap prevalent in these economies in order to accelerate growth. This result is further verified by employing a robustness estimation through the use of the *fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS)* approach. The result is still in consonance with that of the ARDL long-run result, except for remittances which exerts a negative but insignificant effect on economic growth of the two economies.

Further analysis was to ascertain the nature of the causal relationship between external capital sources and economic growth in Nigeria and Ghana. Findings from the Dumitrescu-Hurlin Granger causality test indicates that all the external capital sources cause economic growth – a unidirectional causality between external debt and economic growth; a bidirectional causality between remittances and economic growth; a unidirectional causality between foreign direct investment and economic growth; and a bidirectional causality between official development assistance/aid and economic growth. Since it is observed that the external capital sources cause economic growth, and they exert positive and significant long-run effect on economic growth of Nigeria and Ghana, the study concludes that external capital inflows are beneficial to the growth of the economy of Nigeria and Ghana as they aid in filling the savings-investment gap that is prevalent in these economies.

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